

LEARNING DIFFICULTIES OF IMMIGRANT CHILDREN: AN ACTION RESEARCH IN A MUNICIPAL SCHOOL IN ITAPEMA, SANTA CATARINA

DIFICULDADES DE APRENDIZAJE DE LOS NIÑOS INMIGRANTES: UNA INVESTIGACIÓN-ACCIÓN EN UNA ESCUELA MUNICIPAL DE ITAPEMA, SANTA CATARINA

DIFICULDADES DE APRENDIZAGEM DE CRIANÇAS IMIGRANTES: UMA PESQUISA-AÇÃO EM ESCOLA MUNICIPAL DE ITAPEMA, SANTA CATARINA

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Abstract

This study deals with the learning difficulties experienced by immigrant children in the school context. The article aims to report on a psycho-pedagogical intervention focused on the learning difficulties of immigrant children in an elementary school. It is an action research conducted in a municipal school in Itapema, Santa Catarina, Brazil. A total of nine interventions were carried out between May and September 2024, involving 107 participants, both managers and teachers of Elementary School I, as well as immigrant children. The interventions with teachers aimed to help them recognize the heterogeneity of students, developing the skills and competencies necessary to better address the learning difficulties presented by immigrant students. The interventions conducted with children, through activities such as rhyming games, "syllable catch," phonological and word recognition games, and discussion circles, contributed to developing socio-emotional and relational skills. These activities demonstrated a positive response from students to the psychopedagogical interventions implemented, reflected in greater engagement in the teaching-learning process and increased interest in knowledge. A limitation of this study was the lack of contact with the families of immigrant children, as well as the time constraints for conducting the research. Advancing studies on this topic is necessary to avoid neglecting the humanity of immigrant children. Without such progress, schools risk reinforcing violent and discriminatory practices rather than fostering institutions grounded in diversity, welcoming, integration, and inclusion of these children.

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Keywords: Immigrants; Children; Learning difficulties.

Resumen

Este estudio aborda las dificultades de aprendizaje que experimentan los niños inmigrantes en el contexto escolar. El artículo pretende informar sobre una intervención psicopedagógica centrada en las dificultades de aprendizaje de los niños inmigrantes en una escuela primaria. Se trata de una investigación-acción realizada en una escuela municipal de Itapema, Santa Catarina, Brasil. Se llevaron a cabo nueve intervenciones, entre mayo y septiembre de 2024, con 107 participantes, tanto directivos como profesores de la Escuela Primaria I, así como niños inmigrantes. Las intervenciones con los docentes buscaron ayudarles a reconocer la heterogeneidad de los estudiantes, desarrollando competencias y habilidades necesarias para abordar las dificultades de aprendizaje presentadas por los estudiantes inmigrantes. Las intervenciones realizadas con los niños, a través de juegos de rimas, “atrapa sílabas,” juegos fonológicos y de reconocimiento de palabras, y círculos de conversación, contribuyeron al desarrollo de habilidades socioemocionales y relacionales. Estas actividades indicaron una respuesta positiva de los estudiantes a las intervenciones psicopedagógicas implementadas, reflejada en un mayor compromiso con el proceso de enseñanza-aprendizaje y un mayor interés por el conocimiento. Una limitación de este estudio fue la falta de contacto con las familias de los niños inmigrantes, así como las restricciones de tiempo para la investigación. Avanzar en estudios es necesario para no arriesgarse a ignorar la humanidad de los niños inmigrantes. De lo contrario, las escuelas podrían convertirse en instituciones que refuercen prácticas violentas y discriminatorias en lugar de promover la diversidad, la acogida, la integración y la inclusión de estos niños.

Palabras clave: Inmigrantes; Niños; Dificultades de aprendizaje.

Resumo

O presente estudo aborda as dificuldades de aprendizagem no contexto escolar vivenciadas por crianças imigrantes. O artigo visa relatar uma intervenção psicopedagógica focada nas dificuldades de aprendizagem de crianças imigrantes de uma escola de ensino fundamental. Trata-se de uma pesquisa-ação realizada em uma escola municipal de Itapema, Santa Catarina, Brasil. Foram realizadas 09 (nove) intervenções, entre os meses de maio e setembro de 2024, envolvendo 107 participantes, tanto gestores e professores do Ensino Fundamental I, quanto crianças imigrantes. As intervenções junto aos professores buscaram contribuir para que percebessem a heterogeneidade dos alunos, desenvolvendo competências e habilidades necessárias para lidar de uma melhor forma com as dificuldades de aprendizagem apresentadas pelos estudantes imigrantes. As intervenções realizadas com as crianças, por meio de atividades como jogos com rimas, “pega sílabas”, jogo fonológico e de reconhecimento de palavras e rodas de conversas, contribuíram para o desenvolver habilidades socioemocionais e relacionais e indicam uma resposta positiva dos estudantes às intervenções psicopedagógicas implementadas, refletida em maior envolvimento no processo de ensino-aprendizagem e no interesse pelo conhecimento. Como limitação do presente estudo destaca-se a ausência de contato com as famílias das crianças imigrantes, bem como a restrição de tempo para a realização do presente estudo. O avanço de pesquisas nessa temática é necessário para não arriscarmos negligenciar a humanidade das crianças imigrantes, fazendo com que, ao invés de termos escolas pautadas na diversidade, no acolhimento, integração e inclusão destas crianças, tenhamos instituições escolares que reforçam práticas violentas e discriminatórias.

Palavras-chave Imigrantes; Crianças; Dificuldades de aprendizagem.

Introduction

This paper addresses the topic of learning difficulties. We are more specifically interested in the learning difficulties in the school context experienced by immigrant children, which constitute a topic of great relevance in the educational field. These difficulties, sometimes manifested in problems with reading, writing, calculation, among others, affect the performance of immigrant students, leading to school failure and disinterest in formal education.

According to Chemin, Filippim and Abrahão (2021), the town of Itapema, in the state of Santa Catarina, has been undergoing a process of increasing tourist appreciation. Along with the city's tourist growth, employment opportunities also arise, becoming another attraction for the migrant population who perceive a possibility of improving their living conditions.

The migratory process of these families also creates new challenges for schools, as children from other cultures, who speak another language, and who are experiencing a new psychosocial reality, tend to be negatively impacted in their pedagogical development (Russo; Mendes; Borri-Anadon, 2020; Rocha; Mendes, 2023). Considering this reality, in order to address the learning difficulties in the school context experienced by immigrant children, it was also necessary to consider the ongoing training of teachers. Given the demands of these children, providing a solid education and a broad general culture, so that these professionals can deal with the data present in the student's culture, especially regarding the knowledge they bring from other experiences, worldviews and the readings they make of this world, is essential (Masuyama; Rinaldi, 2017; Pimentel; Ribeiro, 2021; Vieira; Miguel, 2020; Da Rosa; Furlan, 2023).

In this context, this paper addresses the reality of children and teachers in Elementary School I at a municipal school in the city of Itapema. There was a focus on the teaching and learning process of students who participate in a municipal project aimed at students who are illiterate and who are in an age and grade that is disproportionate to their school year. The project also aims to develop socio-emotional skills to enable more effective inclusion in the school environment. In view of this reality,

throughout the school year, the teachers in charge of the 3rd, 4th and 5th grades receive immigrant students who are lagging behind and/or have difficulties. These students attend the project, which is run twice a week in the afternoon by a pedagogue, aiming to contribute to the teaching-learning process of these students and help overcome existing barriers, especially when it comes to inclusive education.

This study is based on the assumption that every individual who is part of the school is affected by it, and that school pedagogical practice should be based on diversity, based on the principles of welcoming, integrating, and including all students. Therefore, it is essential to overcome the mechanisms of exclusion still present in the school environment and observe, through different perspectives, how relationships that affect individuals develop. The mere presence of immigrant students of diverse origins and backgrounds in school can reinforce violent and discriminatory practices already overcome in other contexts. Therefore, pedagogical proposals and methodologies aligned with the principles of diversity, decoloniality, and socio-emotional practices must be taught. Promoting a truly inclusive school environment is essential. Therefore:

school inclusion makes each of us an agent, an articulator, a multiplier of our actions. Collaboration, partnership, and solidarity are part of this context in which the so-called inclusive school, like a unit-company, unites everyone around the same objectives and the same goals. (Lunardi-Lazzarin; Hermes, 2015, p. 541)

Thus, it is understood that respecting the origins of diverse identities and experiences means adopting a stance of inclusion, or ensuring a less exclusive space. Therefore, the teaching and learning process is a complex reality. Every day, schools play a fundamental role in the comprehensive development of students. They require qualified and prepared professionals to provide a quality education, meet the needs of immigrant children, and address the diversity of ideas present in the school environment and in the classroom itself (Ribeiro; Oliveira, 2019; Azevedo; Amaral, 2021).

Therefore, it is necessary to provide training that encourages a critical-reflective perspective, with collective dimensions that promote the qualification of teachers capable of transforming the school into a space for the construction of knowledge and the production of knowledge (Abu-El-Haj; Fialho, 2019; Vieira; Miguel, 2020; Silva;

Santos, 2024). Considering the importance of schools for children's development, their essential role in the inclusion and integration of immigrant children, as well as in the development of a culture of peace and respect for differences in our society, we were interested in conducting this research. The present study began with the following question: what has caused the learning difficulties of immigrant children, and how can teachers contribute?

This paper aims to report on a psychopedagogical intervention focused on the learning difficulties of immigrant children at an elementary school in Itapema, Santa Catarina. The specific objectives were: to identify the main factors that influence the learning difficulties of immigrant children, as well as to explore cultural, social, linguistic and emotional elements that may be interfering with the academic performance of these children; and to explore effective pedagogical strategies for teachers in supporting immigrant children with learning difficulties.

There is no consensus in the academic world about the meaning of learning difficulties, according to the Diagnostic Manual of Mental Disorders - DSM V (American Psychiatric Association - APA, 2014), which in turn characterizes persistent and detrimental difficulties in basic reading, writing, and/or mathematics skills, with performance in these skills below average for age. From an educational perspective, learning difficulties are characterized by specific challenges that can affect the process of learning reading, writing, arithmetic, and other cognitive and social skills (Correia; Martins, 2005; Azevedo, 2021; Paula et al., 2024). This can lead to feelings of frustration, academic failure, and dropout, consequently, harming students throughout life, weakening future professional performance (Navarro et al., 2016; Paula et al., 2024).

For international migrant students, particularly Latin American students, cultural issues emerge significantly in this process, as culture is transmitted, revised, and recreated within the family and other social institutions, and it is at school that it is reflected in the enculturation process and interpersonal relationships. Enculturation is a complex social process that involves both the intentional transmission of knowledge and values, carried out by social agents such as educators and family members, and the incidental acquisition of knowledge through participation in everyday social practices.

The former occurs systematically, while the latter is more unsystematic and informal. We can learn systematically, with an instructor, who teaches us the correct steps and helps us avoid mistakes. But we can also learn informally, by observing others and trying to imitate them. In both cases, we are internalizing new behavior and learning to be part of a social group (Assis; Nepomuceno, 2008).

Brazilian law stipulates that foreigners should have the same right to access education as Brazilian children and adolescents, as set forth in the Federal Constitution (Brazil, 1988), the Statute of Children and Adolescents (Brazil, 1990), the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (Brazil, 1996), and the Migration Law (Brazil, 2017). Furthermore, the Refugee Law (Brazil, 1997) states that a lack of documentation, due to their unfavorable situation, should not be an obstacle for these children to enter school. Therefore, it is determined by law that every child, immigrant or not, should have access to the same quality, free education.

The National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) is a document that establishes the essential competencies and skills that must be taught in all schools in the country, at all levels. Regarding immigrant students, the BNCC advocates valuing cultural diversity, respecting ethnic and cultural differences, and welcoming immigrants and refugees. The BNCC emphasizes the importance of guaranteeing access to education for all immigrants, regardless of their legal status in the country. Furthermore, the document emphasizes the importance of teaching Portuguese as a second language so that immigrants can communicate effectively and integrate into Brazilian society (Brasil, 2018).

Another point highlighted by the BNCC is the importance of teaching the history and culture of immigrant peoples, both from a Brazilian perspective and from their origins, for the understanding and appreciation of cultural diversity. It affirms the importance of welcoming and valuing cultural diversity, including inclusion and special attention to immigrants, seeking to guarantee their basic rights, including access to education and respect for their culture and identity (Brazil, 2018).

Brazil is considered a welcoming country for immigrant and/or refugee children and their families by law, but there are still cases where they face difficulties in accessing education, healthcare, and housing. The difficulties of migrant and refugee children are

compounded by other barriers that compound this access, such as language barriers, lack of documentation, parental ignorance of rights, racism, xenophobia, and professional performance that is neither respected nor valued, disregarding the academic background of family members who arrive here and need to work (Dos Santos; Alves. Machado, 2022; Franzon; Deniz; Contreras, 2023). In this aspect, cultural, linguistic specificities and psychosocial aspects must be considered, which involve the particular situation of each immigrant student, all of these factors can be aggravating factors in their pedagogical development (Russo; Mendes; Borri-Anadon, 2020; Rocha; Mendes, 2023).

It's essential that professionals be aware of psychosocial aspects to promote a healthy and safe learning environment for their students. Teachers must be facilitators, seeking to help each student advance in their learning process. However, there are limits that everyone will consider. Creativity lies in finding ways to engage immigrant students with new approaches offered by educators in the classroom.

we can all be creative because we can generate ideas, whether simple or complex; however, we should not confuse creativity with innovation, because innovation is the organizational capacity to transform a good idea into a product, service or process, to which the success factor must always be added, focused on each scenario. (Rajadell, 2012, p. 108)

According to researches focused on immigrant children in elementary school, we see that the greatest challenge for teachers, and even for the children themselves, is the language, the lack of understanding that, consequently, ends up hindering the immigrant child's learning process (Tomazzeti, 2004; Franzon; Deniz; Contreras, 2023; Neves, 2018).

Thus, we understand that the best curriculum is to reflect the learner's daily life, a dialogue with everyday life. Even with inclusive proposals, in some situations, the presence of a mediator or educational psychologist to assist the teacher is always welcome, but it is not always possible to have such a professional nearby. The reality of education often imposes limits on pedagogical practice that can only be overcome by the love and professional preparation of those who work there.

This consequently necessitates changes in the relationships between school and knowledge, between teacher and student, and between education and the contemporary world. In addition to connecting with current transformations, contemporary times demand an understanding of the different dynamics that occur in the teaching and learning process in order to develop pedagogical strategies appropriate to the student's reality. (Cunha, 2018, p. 54)

We understand that there are practices committed to inclusive, welcoming, and respectful education, and that every effort made by teachers and teaching teams is worthwhile. We advocate that ongoing teacher training, from a multicultural perspective and grounded in intercultural dialogue, can make educational processes more meaningful for all children and, especially, welcoming for immigrant children.

In our current global, digital, and complex society, as Do Carmo (2023) highlights, schools play an irreplaceable role in the socio-emotional development of children and adolescents. Several studies (Mesquita, Batista, Silva, 2019; Silva, 2022; Do Carmo, 2023) have shown that the school environment influences the development of students' socio-emotional skills, which is fundamental to their overall development. If schools can foster a safe and welcoming environment that values empathy, communication, and conflict resolution, students will feel safe and able to learn and develop, which will benefit them in all areas of their lives.

In this context, psychopedagogy can act as a mediator between the teacher, the student, and the teaching-learning process, aiming to promote effective interaction between these elements. This field proposes and develops tools that aim to facilitate educational changes, encouraging the discovery and development of students' capabilities. By helping students understand and interpret the world around them, psychopedagogy prevents many children from being stigmatized or excluded from the learning process, which could result in academic and social failure. Thus, psychopedagogy is a fundamental area in educational institutions, implementing innovations that enhance the teaching-learning process.

When we talk about school inclusion, we refer to developing all possible ways to minimize exclusion throughout the educational process, maximizing student participation in the educational process, and producing a conscious education for all, considering all origins and barriers to the learning process (Santos; Paulino, 2008).

Methodological path

This study is an action research study conducted at a municipal school in Itapema, Santa Catarina. This intervention, therefore, was carried out through a dialogue between researchers and participants, making them subjects of the discussion and the proposed study (Senna; Santos; Pinto, 2018; Thiollent; Colette, 2020). This methodological strategy is justified by the understanding that such a research model can contribute to greater articulation between universities and society, contributing to an update of the university, towards a deepening of democracy, as well as enabling Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to devise strategies that can be used to solve local, national, and global problems (Thiollent; Colette, 2020).

We chose not to reveal the name of the school or the project in which the immigrant students participate, so as not to risk compromising the anonymity of the study participants. Before the intervention, the research project was submitted for review through Plataforma Brasil and approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Santa Catarina (consolidated opinion CAAE 79680824.0.0000.0121). Throughout the research, all recommendations of resolution 510/16 of the National Health Council (Brazil, 2016) were respected.

A total of 9 interventions were conducted between May and September 2024. Each intervention lasted an average of 4 hours. These actions involved 107 participants, including teachers and administrators, as well as children, with a focus on immigrant children.

The intervention was conducted in two phases. The first phase involved 5 interventions. 67 participants took part in this phase of the study, including administrators and elementary school teachers, including 1st-5th grade teachers (pedagogues), Humanities teachers (who teach History and Geography) (pedagogues), and teachers (graduates) in the following areas: Art, Physical Education, English, and Spanish.

The first meeting, held during a pedagogical meeting, was attended by all teachers and administrators. Teachers participated in the other interventions based on their availability. These were structured through ongoing training, focusing on executive functions, and also included some syllabic-level strategies that would

contribute to teachers' performance and significantly impact learning. We also sought to observe and recognize the heterogeneity of the students. These meetings with teachers included projectors, printed materials, music, and videos. Activities were also monitored during class planning, along with observation and participation.

In the second stage, 04 interventions were conducted. Forty children participated in this study: 20 from 4th and 5th grade, and the remainder from 6th and 7th grade. Of these, 10 were Latin American immigrant students (Haitian, Venezuelan, and Argentinean). This second stage of the intervention was carried out based on the demand identified with the teachers, as it became clear that a problem in the school unit involved immigrant students, and that the learning difficulties they presented were not only due to a language barrier, but also due to interpersonal issues.

Due to the immigrant students' learning difficulties, they participated in after-school tutoring offered by the school. The project serves children in grades 4th through 7th. On Mondays and Tuesdays, the project teacher works with 4th and 5th graders, and on Thursdays and Fridays, with 6th and 7th graders. Thus, based on the initial needs identified in the study, this project aimed at children with learning difficulties led to work with immigrant students focusing on interpersonal relationships to overcome language, as well as social and cultural barriers.

Although the focus of this action research is the learning difficulties experienced by immigrant children, it was agreed with the teacher responsible for the project that the interventions would involve the entire class of this tutoring project. The decision was made to develop the intervention within the project aimed at children with learning difficulties because it allows for fewer students than in a regular classroom.

Through activities such as rhyming games, syllable matching, phonological and word recognition games, and conversation circles, the aim was to develop socio-emotional and relational skills, as well as foster a more positive attitude in students. Reducing the distance between teacher and student was also a guiding objective of this intervention.

Results

Through dialogue with representatives of the school administration and the teaching staff, it was possible to identify that initial teacher training constitutes the first necessary intervention. Reports revealed that teachers in the Early Years (1st to 5th grades) have a practice focused on the comprehensive education of students and have access to teaching materials and training provided by the Municipal Department of Education (SME). However, this practice sometimes presents gaps in implementing strategies that address the specific needs of students with learning difficulties, learning disorders, and disabilities, which, consequently, has impacted the learning of immigrant children. This was evident in the reports of the school's teaching staff, who expressed concern about the learning of immigrant students.

On the other hand, the teaching staff reports a prevalence of inattention among students in general, particularly among those in the Early Years, aged 7 to 12. The testimonies presented by teachers and administrators suggested that these children's inattention was due to lack of discipline. This problem was identified by the researchers through monitoring classes. Thus, it was possible to observe a fragility in student behavior in the classroom, resulting in frequent episodes of restlessness and disorder, which significantly compromise the learning process.

Based on classroom observations, it was also identified that some teachers require knowledge of neuropsychopedagogy, particularly regarding executive functions, with an emphasis on working memory, inhibitory control, and cognitive flexibility. As Diamond (2013) points out, these functions play a fundamental role in children's learning, as they directly influence their ability to focus attention, recall relevant information, control impulses, and solve problems. It was observed that some teachers, during the implementation of pedagogical proposals, demonstrate limitations both in implementing these proposals and in developing more engaging and inclusive activities that consider the diversity and heterogeneity of students.

Regarding the second phase of this action research, with students in the project aimed at those with learning disabilities, which predominantly involves immigrant students, the first day was dedicated to presentations. A presentation and a dynamic conversation with the students were held, and each student introduced themselves through the string dynamic. Each student took the string, wrapped it around their finger, and then, after introducing themselves, tossed the ball of string to another student. This activity aimed to further integrate the class. The tangle of crisscrossed strings that formed in the classroom demonstrated the diversity and plurality of the classroom, as well as the multiculturalism present in each student's development.

On the second and third days of the intervention, as previously agreed with the teacher and tailored to her planning, the activities involved a smaller group, 3rd and 4th graders, which included 3 Venezuelan immigrant students. Two activities were conducted: "Syllable Matching" and "Rhyming Lynx," both of which sought to associate rhyming words.

In the "Syllable Matching" game, children were encouraged to associate images with syllable sounds and identify the corresponding syllable from the drawings presented. This playful activity practiced listening and recognition of the initial syllables of words, developing attention and visual perception, skills necessary for learning.

"Rhyming Lynx" allowed them to explore both phonological criteria, through the use of picture cards, and word recognition. Through these activities, which involved rhyming words, students were able to identify the syllable corresponding to the drawing, practice the sounds of the initial syllable, perform visual perception, develop visual attention, as well as develop logical reasoning.

On the fourth and final day of intervention with the children, a Social-Emotional Education activity was held, involving all the children participating in the project aimed at students with learning disabilities. On this occasion, they were encouraged to express their feelings. To this end, a box containing various qualities was provided: optimism, courage, integrity, respect, honesty, humility, generosity, discipline, creativity, focus, determination, self-confidence, patience, compassion, and justice. Each quality contained a brief explanation of each characteristic.

As the box containing the qualities was passed from one child to another, each student removed a quality, read it, and commented on whether or not they identified

with serious characteristics. Integrity, focus, and generosity were characteristics that some of the children were unfamiliar with. Some doubts about whether generosity could be considered. Given the children's difficulties, practical examples were presented, based on situations they had experienced, as an intuitive way to clarify the meaning of the term and demonstrate the importance of these characteristics. The aim was to develop socio-emotional skills of self-management, kindness towards others, emotional resilience, engagement with others and openness to new things.

At the end of the intervention, we observed strong student enthusiasm and positive feedback on the activities. No tests or assessments were administered to the students, as the goal of social-emotional skills was to develop more inclusive practices, not to measure who possesses them. With this intervention, we hope to encourage reflection among teachers and students toward a more inclusive school environment that fosters positive dialogue and relationships.

Discussion

The topic of learning difficulties seems relevant to all educators who work with students in regular classrooms. They are professionals who must embrace and address the situation, but who also need constant encouragement regarding their practice and methodological adaptations, especially when this learning difficulty is related to the immigrant student. In the specific case of the school where this study was conducted, although having a project designed for children with learning difficulties is considered a step forward, we still find teachers in the classroom who struggle to work with such students, who arrive speaking another language and have trouble relating to others, resulting in learning obstacles. These results have also been found in other studies (Neves, 2018; Abu-El-Haj; Fialho, 2019; Ribeiro; Oliveira, 2019; Russo, Mendes, Borri-Anadon, 2020; Azevedo; Amaral, 2021; Franzon; Deniz; Contrera, 2023).

Therefore, through interventions with teachers, we sought to help them understand the heterogeneity of their students, developing the skills and abilities necessary to better address the learning difficulties presented by immigrant students. The meetings served as a form of support for teachers, providing an opportunity to

exchange practical and theoretical experiences regarding the challenges of working with students who have learning difficulties. This need for ongoing teacher training is highlighted by various authors (Masuyama; Rinaldi, 2017; Ribeiro; Oliveira, 2019; Vieira; Miguel, 2020; Azevedo; Amaral, 2021; Da Rosa; Furlan, 2023; Silva; Santos, 2024) as a strategy for teachers to better address the data present in the immigrant students' culture, exploring their experiences and worldviews.

Regarding the concerns raised by teachers regarding students' inattention, restlessness, and disorderliness that compromise learning, in the case of immigrant children, as highlighted by Russo, Mendes, and Borri-Anadon (2020) and Rocha and Mendes (2023), it is necessary to understand the specific situation of each immigrant student, as cultural, linguistic, and psychosocial issues can aggravate their pedagogical development.

Another notable result of this action research concerns the process of exclusion experienced by immigrant children in the school context. Through the interventions, it was evident that professionals began to work harder to deconstruct stigmas and prejudices toward immigrant students. As Neves (2018) emphasizes, schools must recognize and value the cultural differences of their students and be prepared to promote intercultural education to foster respectful coexistence among their members. Tomazzeti (2004), Neves (2018) and Franzon, Deniz and Contreras (2023) add that the language barrier needs to be overcome, so as not to compromise the immigrant child's learning process.

The school must also create a favorable environment for the development of students' socio-emotional skills (Mesquita; Batista; Silva, 2019; Silva, 2022; Do Carmo, 2023), fostering a safe and welcoming environment that values empathy, communication, and conflict resolution. As Silva and Santos (2024) point out, educating, caring, and playing in early childhood education are inseparable and fundamental to child development. Given these considerations, it was observed that there were theoretical and methodological advances on the part of the teacher responsible for the project in which immigrant children with learning difficulties participate. She has shown greater commitment, and the teaching strategies used are aligned with the students' expectations.

Final Considerations

Our psychopedagogical activities sought to promote learning, with a special focus on supporting immigrant students who experience learning delays or difficulties in socializing with their peers. This work aimed to strengthen a more positive attitude and bridge the gap between teacher and student. Throughout the activities, we sought to introduce students to the world of knowledge in a fun and creative way, providing them with tools to navigate the world of literacy with confidence and enthusiasm.

Throughout the process, we maintained a constant dialogue with teachers, administrators, and especially with the teacher leading the project for children with learning difficulties, encouraging her to continue. We recognize that each teacher is responsible for creating opportunities for their students to enter the world of literacy, and we strive to support them so that this integration occurs in a welcoming and effective manner.

We closely monitored the knowledge construction process of immigrant children, who brought with them diverse histories and school experiences. We constantly reviewed and adjusted our practices, striving to create a welcoming environment where information was organized in an accessible way, but without oversimplification. In this context, peer interaction proved essential for students to develop mutual understanding, reflecting on ideas, intentions, beliefs, and emotions. We noticed that, through interaction, they began to understand their actions and communicate with teachers and peers more consciously, becoming active participants in the teaching-learning process.

In all activities, students were invited to construct their learning, whether orally or in writing, establishing connections between both forms of expression. This task was not easy for them, as participating in a project specifically for children with learning difficulties sometimes exacerbated feelings of exclusion from the class. Given these circumstances, we seek to highlight the comprehensive role of the school psychopedagogue, who acts as a mediator in literacy moments, encouraging the learning of reading and writing and motivating students to socialize without fear of exclusion or embarrassment.

To guide teachers working with students with learning disabilities, we emphasize the importance of ongoing contact with families, adopting a broader perspective that considers the student's immediate contexts. We believe that families play a central role in this process and can help reduce labels that limit the development of children with learning disabilities.

We conclude that, throughout this action research, we observed the students' interests and their constantly evolving psychological, intellectual, and social needs. Although the actions taken were limited to what was feasible in the short period of coexistence, the experience fostered a deeper understanding and respect for different cultures. This process involved acceptance, attentive listening, and appreciation of each student's individual limitations and trajectories, strengthening our commitment to inclusive and culturally sensitive education.

However, we observed the limitation represented by the lack of active family participation. In this sense, it would be important to continue the work to facilitate direct contact with parents or guardians, enabling a more accurate analysis of students' learning difficulties. It is essential, therefore, that Early Years teachers, when facing such challenges in the classroom, are familiar with appropriate interventions and pedagogical measures, approaching the learning process in a way that fosters students' comprehensive development.

It is crucial to consider social relationships and intercultural dialogue as fundamental to promoting mutual learning. The educational psychologist, however, does not offer ready-made answers. What occurred throughout this action research was the result of collective work, involving administrators, technical staff, teachers, students, support staff, and families. Thus, the interdisciplinarity that permeates this experience enriched the conceptual construction and emphasized the importance of inclusion processes for immigrant students in learning.

It is recommended that future studies on immigrant children's learning difficulties further explore the school-family relationship, teacher training, and the institutional challenges facing these teachers. Further studies should combine techniques from both qualitative and quantitative methodologies to better assess the effects of interventions. Further research on this topic is necessary to avoid neglecting

the humanity of immigrant children, resulting in schools that reinforce violent and discriminatory practices instead of schools focused on diversity, welcoming, integrating, and including all students.

References

ABU-EL-HAJ, M. F.; FIALHO, L. M. F. Formação docente e práticas pedagógicas multiculturais críticas. **Revista Educação em Questão**, v.57, n.53, p.e17109, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21680/1981-1802.2019v57n53ID17109>

AMERICAN PSYCHIATRIC ASSOCIATION - APA. **Manual diagnóstico e estatístico de transtornos mentais: DSM-5**. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2014.

ASSIS, C. L.; NEPOMUCENO, C. N. Processos Culturais: Endoculturação e Aculturação. **Estudos Contemporâneos de Cultura**, v.8, 2008.

AZEVEDO, G. X. Dificuldades de aprendizagem: uma revisão de literatura. **Educação em Debate**, v.1, n.84, p.38-52, 2021. Disponível em: <https://periodicos.ufc.br/educacaoemdebate/article/view/72559>

AZEVEDO, R. S.; AMARAL, C. T. As dimensões da docência no ensino às crianças imigrantes e refugiadas: estudo de caso com professoras em Goiânia. **Revista Inter-Ação**, v.46, n.2, p.762-777, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5216/ia.v46i2.67964>

BRASIL. **Constituição da República Federativa do Brasil**. Brasília, DF: Presidência da República, 1988. Disponível em: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/constituicao/constituicao.htm Acesso em: 10 out. 2024.

BRASIL. **Lei n. 8069, 13 de julho de 1990**. Dispõe sobre o Estatuto da Criança e do Adolescente e dá outras providências. Brasília, DF: Câmara, 1990. Disponível em: <https://www2.camara.leg.br/legin/fed/lei/1990/lei-8069-13-julho-1990-372211-publicacaooriginal-1-pl.html> Acesso em: 10 out. 2024.

BRASIL. **Lei n. 9394, 20 de dezembro de 1996**. Estabelece as diretrizes e bases da educação nacional. Brasília, DF: Ministério da Educação, 1996. Disponível em: http://portal.mec.gov.br/seesp/arquivos/pdf/lei9394_ldbn1.pdf Acesso em: 10 out. 2024.

BRASIL. **Lei n. 9.474, de 22 de julho de 1997**. Define mecanismos para a implementação do Estatuto dos Refugiados de 1951, e determina outras providências. Brasília, DF: Presidência da República, 1997. Disponível em: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/l9474.htm Acesso em: 10 out. 2024.

BRASIL. **Resolução nº 510/2016**. Dispõe sobre a pesquisa em Ciências Humanas e Sociais. Brasília, DF: Ministério da Saúde, 2016. Disponível em: <https://www.gov.br/conselho-nacional-de-saude/pt-br/atos-normativos/resolucoes/2016/resolucao-no-510.pdf/view> Acesso em: 10 out. 2024.

BRASIL. **Lei n. 13445, 24 de maio de 2017**. Institui a Lei de Migração. Brasília, DF: Presidência da República, 2017. Disponível em: <https://legislacao.presidencia.gov.br/atos/?tipo=LEI&numero=13445&ano=2017&ato=fadMTRU5EeZpWTbd4> Acesso em: 10 out. 2024.

BRASIL. **Base Nacional Comum Curricular**: Educação é a base. Brasília, DF: Ministério da Educação, 2018. Disponível em: https://www.gov.br/mec/pt-br/escola-em-tempo-integral/BNCC_EI_EF_110518_versaofinal.pdf Acesso em: 10 out. 2024.

CHEMIN, M.; FILIPPIM, M. L.; ABRAHÃO, C. M. S. Projeção territorial e pontos de interesse em destinos turísticos da região Sul (Brasil): análise a partir do Mapa do Turismo 2019-2021. **Revista Brasileira de Pesquisa em Turismo**, v.15, n.3, p.e2156, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7784/rbtur.v15i3.2156>

CORREIA, L. M. E MARTINS, A. P. **Dificuldades de Aprendizagem**. O que são? Como entendê-las? **Biblioteca Digital**. Porto: Porto Editora, 2005. Coleção Educação

CUNHA, A. E. **Práticas pedagógicas para a inclusão e diversidade**. 7 ed. Rio de Janeiro: Wak Editora, 2018.

DA ROSA, C.; FURLAN, F. Dificuldades de aprendizagem: o que dizem os psicólogos escolares acerca deste fenômeno? **Monumenta - Revista de Estudos Interdisciplinares**, v.3, n.5, p.42-73, 2023. Disponível em: <https://monumenta.emnuvens.com.br/monumenta/article/view/72>

DIAMOND, A. Executive functions. **Annual Review of Psychology**, v.64, p.135-168, 2013. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-113011-143750>

DO CARMO, W. B. Competências Socioemocionais na Escola: Incertezas e Desafios. **Altus Ciência**, v.17, p.36-48, 2023. Disponível em: <http://revistas.fcjp.edu.br/ojs/index.php/altuscienca/article/view/127>

DOS SANTOS, M. S.; ALVES, R. A. R.; MACHADO, E. E. Relação família-escola de crianças imigrantes na educação infantil: o que as pesquisas (não) têm a dizer? **Revista Teias**, v.23, n.69, p.91-114, 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.12957/teias.2022.66095>

FRANZON, G. K.; DENIZ, C. O.; CONTRERAS, H. H. Crianças imigrantes nas escolas de educação infantil: seus aspectos culturais com enfoque no processo linguístico. **Revista Cactácea, educação e filosofia**. v.3, n.9, p.131-149, 2023. Disponível em: <https://rgt.ifsp.edu.br/ojs/index.php/revistacactacea/article/view/95>

LUNARDI-LAZZARIN, M. L.; HERMES, S. T. Educação Especial, Educação Inclusiva e Pedagogia da Diversidade: celebrar a diversidade! exaltar a tolerância! notabilizar o respeito! proclamar a solidariedade! **Revista Educação Especial**, v.28, n.53, p.531-544, 2015. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5902/1984686X18802>

MASUYAMA P. M. K.; RINALDI, R. P. Formação de professores em exercício: o olhar sobre os problemas de aprendizagem. **Revista NUPEM**, v.9, n.18, p.59-72, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33871/nupem.v9i18.503>

MESQUITA, A. M.; BATISTA, J. B.; SILVA, M. M. O desenvolvimento de emoções e sentimentos e a formação de valores. **Obutchénie. Revista de Didática e Psicologia Pedagógica**, v.3, n.3, p.1-25, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14393/OBv3n3.a2019-51695>

NAVARRO, L.; GERVAI, S.; NAKAYAMA, A.; PRADO, A. S. A dificuldade de aprendizagem e o fracasso escolar. **Jornal of research in special education needs**, n.16, v.s1, p.46-50, 2016. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-3802.12267>

NEVES, A. O. **Política linguística de acolhimento a crianças imigrantes no ensino fundamental**: um estudo de caso. 2018. 185 f. Dissertação (Mestrado em Estudos Linguísticos) – Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Belo Horizonte, 2018.

PAULA, A. J. M.; ROCHA, J. B.; SILVA, L. J. S.; OLIVEIRA, M. A. S.; SANTOS, M. M. F. Desafios na educação escolar observados pelos pibidianos: um estudo de caso sobre dificuldades de aprendizagem e comportamento disruptivo. **Ciência Atual**. v.21, n.2, p.1091-1105, 2024. Disponível em: <https://revista.saojose.br/index.php/cafsj/article/view/736>

PIMENTEL, S. C.; RIBEIRO, S. L. Política de formação de professores para educação inclusiva: reflexões a partir do Plano Nacional de Educação. **Cenas Educacionais**, v.4, p.e11763, 2021. Disponível em: <https://www.revistas.uneb.br/index.php/cenaseducacionais/article/view/11763>

RAJADELL, N. A importância das estratégias didáticas em toda ação formativa. In: SUANNO, M. V. R.; PUIGGRÓS, N. R. (Org.). **Didática e formação de professores: perspectivas e inovações**. Goiânia: CEPED Publicações; PUC Goiás, 2012.

RIBEIRO, S. B. C.; OLIVEIRA, G. M. “¡Es muy difícil! ¡Es muy difícil!” Quando as barreiras linguísticas conduzem à margem a necessidade de um acolhimento intercultural e de uma formação pedagógica em línguas. **RELACult - Revista Latino-Americana de Estudos em Cultura e Sociedade**, v.5, n.esp., p.1-17, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.23899/relacult.v5i5.1105>

ROCHA, S. R. P.; MENDES, G. M. L. O direito à educação de crianças migrantes: incluir ou integrar? **Revista Momento – diálogos em educação**, v.32, n.3, p.21-39, 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14295/momento.v32i03.16035>

RUSSO, K; MENDES, L; BORRI-ANADON, C. Crianças em situação de imigração na escola pública: percepções de docentes. **Caderno de Pesquisa**, v.50, n.175, p.256 -272, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/198053146943>

SANTOS; M.P.; PAULINO, M.M. **Inclusão em Educação: Culturas, Políticas e Práticas**. 2 ed. São Paulo: Cortez, 2008.

SENNA, M.; SANTOS, M. P.; PINTO, R. M. S. C. (Re)viendo culturas, políticas e práticas de inclusão em educação: a formação continuada da gestão municipal de educação por meio da pesquisa ação. **Pesquisa e Prática em Educação Inclusiva**, v.1, n.1, p.116-126, 2018. Disponível em: <https://periodicos.ufam.edu.br/index.php/educacaoInclusiva/article/view/4222>

SILVA, M. M. Crítica à formação de competências socioemocionais na escola. **Revista HISTEDBR On-line**, v.22, n. e022013, p.1-20, 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20396/rho.v22i00.8659871>

SILVA, F. J.; SANTOS, T. R. L. Prática pedagógica das professoras da educação infantil no município de Paragominas/PA. **Cenas Educacionais**, v.7, p.e16933, 2024. Disponível em: <https://www.revistas.uneb.br/index.php/cenaseducacionais/article/view/16933>

THIOLLENT, M. J. M.; COLETTE, M. M. Pesquisa-ação, universidade e sociedade. **Revista Mbote**, v.1, n.1, p.42-66, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47551/mbote.v1i1.9382>

TOMAZZETTI, C. M. **Pedagogia e infância na perspectiva intercultural: implicações para a formação de professores**. 2004. 241 f. Tese (Doutorado em Educação Intercultural e Movimentos Sociais) - Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, 2004.

VIEIRA, C; MIGUEL, G. F. Dificuldade de aprendizagem nas séries iniciais nas escolas. **Revista Panorâmica**, v.30, p.112-122,2020. Disponível em: <https://periodicoscientificos.ufmt.br/revistapanoramica/index.php/revistapanoramica/article/view/1144>